

SCL Test Science Projects for EOSC Future (WP6.3):

COVID-19 metadata findability and interoperability in EOSC (META-COVID)

Protocol of a qualitative study to characterise the contextual metadata and workflows in selected research infrastructures

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The qualitative study planned is part of the Horizon 2020 funded project EOSC Future (<https://eoscfuture.eu/>). In Work Package 6, Task 6.3 of EOSC Future, Test Science Projects (TSP) are specified. Relevant to this protocol is the TSP "COVID-19 metadata findability and interoperability in EOSC" (short: META-COVID). The objective of this TSP is to develop a framework for a metadata model characterising the contextual metadata and especially the research approach followed in the domain represented by each research infrastructure (RI). The intention is to apply an iterative process of consensus building amongst experts drawn from different disciplines in the life sciences and social sciences and humanities. As a first step, semi-structured interviews of representatives of individual participating RIs will be performed by ECRIN.

The study protocol has been structured according to COREQ, the consolidated criteria for reporting qualitative research (checklist for interviews and focus groups; <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/17872937/>).

A. Research team and reflexivity

1. Interviewer/facilitator

The semi-structured interviews will be conducted by three (3) experts from the European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network (ECRIN): Maria Panagiotopoulou (M.P.), Steve Canham (S.C.), Christian Ohmann (C.O.).

2. Credentials

The researchers' credentials are PhD, MSc, BA for M.P., Prof., PhD, diploma for C.O. and MSc, BA for S.C.

3. Occupation

At the time of the study the interviewers are employed by ECRIN (M.P. as permanent staff, S.C., C.O. as consultants).

4. Gender

Two interviewers are males and one interviewer female.

5. Experience of training

The 3 interviewers have major experience in training:

M.P.: Major experience in the training and supervision of master's students in the field of biotechnology. Education and training responsible for the conception and realisation of online tutorials in cytogenetics¹. Currently contributing as speaker in workshops and training events in the field of life sciences.

S.C.: Major experience in teaching and training of nurses and other health care staff – largely within psychiatric care – and of management of training programmes, teaching staff, curricular development, and quality management in higher education (1983 to 2001). Large experience in conducting video conference sessions related to publicly funded projects.

C.O.: Major experience in student teaching and training of study nurses and clinical researchers (biostatistics, medical informatics, investigator and principal investigator training). Large experience in planning and conducting video conferences related to publicly funded projects.

6. Relationship established

The study will be performed within the Horizon 2020 funded project EOSC Future and here within the test science project "META-COVID". Participants of the interviews are representatives from the partners of this project. Work within the test science project has already started prior to this study, so a professional relationship is already established. The relationship between the interviewers from ECRIN and the interviewees from the RIs can be characterised as peer-to-peer, so in principle and essentially colleagues will be interviewed for the purpose of the project.

7. Participant knowledge of the interviewers

The reasons for doing the research are part of the description of work for the test science project META-COVID and are therefore known to the participants.

8. Interviewer characteristics

Reasons and interest in this study are originating from the test science project META-COVID.

B. Study design

9. Methodological orientation and theory

The study will be based on content analysis, a procedure systematically organising data into structured formats.

10. Sampling

All research infrastructures participating in the test science project were selected as participants of this study. From the life sciences, the following infrastructures will be included:

¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZG5ssFNI3Jc>

- ECRIN
- BBMRI
- EATRIS
- EU-Openscreen
- EMBL

From social sciences and humanities the following infrastructures will be included:

- CESSDA (represented by the Finnish Social Science Data Archive, FSD)
- CLARIN

In these infrastructures senior experts will be identified, able to cover the metadata schemas used in their infrastructure and scientific domain (including contextual metadata) and the workflow performed in tasks and projects related to the infrastructure and to the scientific domain it represents.

11. Methods of approach

The participating RIs will be approached through the TSP representatives per e-mail. Background material (including a protocol, an interview guide and an information sheet) will be sent to the META-COVID representatives of each RI. In a preparatory TC with representatives from the RI, suitable experts will be identified and nominated for the semi-structured interviews. These interviews will be performed as video conferences.

12. Sample size

All 7 research infrastructures participating in the test science project will be included in the study.

13. Non-participation

Because the study is part of the META-COVID work plan, agreed by all the partners, there will be no dropouts.

14. Setting of data collection

Data are collected during the video conference and recorded by the interviewer with the help of a structured data sheet.

15. Presence of non-participants

No one else will be present at the video conferences besides the participants (interviewers, interviewees).

16. Description of sample

Important characteristics of the participating infrastructures are:

Infrastructure	Characteristics
ECRIN	The European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network (ECRIN) is a not-for-profit intergovernmental organisation that supports the conduct of multinational clinical trials in Europe (ECRIN-ERIC).
BBMRI	BBMRI is the European research infrastructure for biobanking (BBMRI-ERIC).
EATRIS	EATRIS is the European research infrastructure for translational medicine (EATRIS-ERIC).
EU-Openscreen	EU-Openscreen is a not-for-profit European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) for chemical biology and early drug discovery.
EMBL	EMBL is an intergovernmental organisation with more than 80 independent research groups covering the spectrum of molecular biology.

CESSDA (represented by the Finnish Social Science Data Archive)	CESSDA - the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives - provides large-scale, integrated and sustainable data services to the social sciences. In the project, CESSDA is represented by the Finnish Social Science Data Archive.
CLARIN	CLARIN – the research infrastructure for language as social and cultural data (CLARIN-ERIC). In META-COVID, the University of Antwerp is participating as part of CLARIN.

17. Interview guide

An interview guide for the semi-structured interviews will be provided by the authors. The guide will be piloted with two infrastructures, within ECRIN itself and with BBMRI.

18. Repeat interviews

Repeated interviews are not foreseen.

19. Audio/virtual recording

The video conferences related to the semi-structured interviews will be recorded but the recording will not be shared beyond the authors. They will be destroyed once the study is complete, and the final report has been written.

20. Field notes

No field notes will be made during the semi-structured interviews.

21. Duration

Duration of the semi-structured interview will be around 60 minutes. The preparatory interview for clarifying the scope of this study and recruiting experts will be scheduled for 30 to 60 minutes.

22. Data saturation

Additional participants will not be recruited.

23. Transcriptions returned

Notes from the interviews will be returned to participants for comments and corrections.

C. Analysis & findings

24. Number of data coders

The data will be coded by the interviewers.

25. Description of the coding tree

The intention is to code the information with existing ontologies/vocabularies and metadata schemas. A list of ontologies/metadata schemas is available from the survey performed within the TSP META-COVID and will be used for this task.

26. Derivation of themes

The themes “contextual metadata” and “workflow” were identified in advance.

27. Software

Ontology browsers will be used to annotate concepts identified in the RIs with ontology concepts. It is planned to use the NCBO Annotator, available within the BioPortal platform, a publicly accessible and easily usable annotator Web service to process raw biomedical English text and identify ontology concepts (<https://bioportal.bioontology.org/annotatorplus>).

28. Participant checking

It is planned to collect feedback on the findings from the participants.

29. Quotations presented

Quotations can be used in the study, provided the source is not identifiable.

30. Date and findings consistent

This is not relevant for the study because data will not be presented to participants in advance.

31. Clarity of major themes

The major themes (“contextual metadata”, “workflow”) will be clearly presented in the findings.

32. Clarity of minor themes

Minor themes that will come up in the interviews will be discussed in the findings.